

STORYTELLING AS A METHOD OF GATHERING PERCEPTIONS AND EXPERIENCES IN HUMAN-CENTERED DESIGN

THE RELATION BETWEEN CHILDREN AND THEIR EYEGLASSES

Iana Garófalo Chaves

The Faculty of Architecture and Urbanism, University of São Paulo – FAUUSP – Brazil

✉ iana@usp.br / iana_chaves@hotmail.com

Agnacilda Silva Rocha

Centro Paula Souza – São Paulo- Brazil

✉ rochaas.d@gmail.com

Cibele Haddad Taralli

The Faculty of Architecture and Urbanism, University of São Paulo – FAUUSP - Brazil

✉ cibelet@usp.br / cibeletaralli@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Given that eyeglasses are specialized orthotic products, we can affirm that their designers contribute to human needs. Among those who wear eyeglass, children require special attention.

The study presented in this article is part of a research that aims to define guidelines for the design of children's eyeglasses. A Human-Centered Design methodology was used for this research, including a Storytelling method to consider the relevant aspects of the product for potential and central users.

This article presents the data collected using this method applied to thirty children. The stories were analyzed, and categories were defined in which it was possible to evaluate emotional, formal, medical, reflexive and functional subjects mentioned by the children. The results and discussion will provide specific and more subjective content that will be combined with other methods to be part of the final design guidelines for children's eyeglasses.

KEYWORDS: *Human-Centered Design, Eyeglasses Design, Storytelling, Product Experience, User Centered Design.*

INTRODUCTION

Eyeglasses are specialized orthotic products, essential for many people's daily existence. As such their designers contribute to human needs.

Currently, eyeglasses are known for their formal aspect and their main corrective functions. However, some argue that the product is has become more of an accessory than a utility, as stated by Bastian (2001, p.35) "Designed for production in large scale, the eyeglasses are objects of industrial design with the refinement of handcrafted pieces...which puts them between design and fashion."

However, beyond aspects of consumption and fashion, eyeglasses should be primarily conceived and designed for those who wear them, as they are personal and fundamental aids to everyday life, and an extension of the body and the human senses. Therefore, the product should be developed considering guidelines that focus on the physical and emotional needs of its wearers.

Among the wearers, children's eyeglasses demand studies and extensive research, as reported by Gozlan (2007, p.52) "the guidance needed for eyeglasses for children is one of the toughest in the daily routine of the optical field, because it requires technical skills and also psychological competence for adapting the child and guiding parents".

Therefore, the design of children's eyeglasses must consider, in addition to formal and aesthetic requirements (ergonomics, anthropometry, performance and usability), perceptual, subjective and emotional aspects that stimulate children's affections for them, making them pleasurable and attractive to use.

The complete research adopts the perspective of Human-Centered Design (HCD), which concerns the way in which people see, interpret and live with some artifact, also considering the meaning as central part of its discourse (Krippendorff, 2000). The author also comments that the application of HCD must be performed in a defined group of stakeholders. For this study, the following stakeholders were established: children who wear eyeglasses; their guardians; the optical attendants; pediatric ophthalmologists and factories/designers of eyeglasses.

The goal of the complete research is to define guidelines for the design of children's eyeglasses. To achieve this goal, different methods will be applied for each one of the stakeholders mentioned before. This paper presents a part of the research and the results of the Storytelling method applied with one of the stakeholder groups: children who wear eyeglasses.

METHOD

Storytelling is considered a narrative tool that is currently used in various fields of knowledge, from pedagogy to marketing, and it is also present in the HCD and User-Centered Design methodologies such as Institute of Design at Stanford (2013) and Suri (2003). According to Parrish (2006), storytelling is a process that combines analysis and synthesis. The stories are always based on extracted facts of life, as personal experiences or observations, and may even go further. Due to this characteristic, the author claims that storytelling is also the process of discovering facts about the narrator of the story. The stories can be seen as a form of research in which, besides the possible analysis, elements of the world are brought together with imagination. This characteristic makes the stories a source of information that can be used by designers to develop their projects.

In terms of storytelling related to a product, Battarbee (2003) states that the stories of products can provide an understanding of how the product interacts with life in lasting and meaningful relationships, and how these relationships can be corroborated through design. The author emphasizes that storytelling can be very useful in the early stages of product design. According to Lin et al (2011), a story must be narrated (in writing or orally) by the person who experienced the event (orally or writing). Otherwise, if told by someone else—even if told truthfully and with emotion—the audience can easily notice that it is not a first hand account.

For this research, the story writing method was used, whereby the user is the author of the stories. This was used as a way to gather information about the product from the group of children through a proposed these that was generic and comprehensive. Thus, the following title was established: "Me and my eyeglasses".

The participants were children of both genders using prescription glasses, in the 7-11 age group; therefore, belonging to the stage of development called concrete operations, as classified by Jean Piaget (1896 - 1980) (Terra, 2013). Another determining factor in this age group was the need for the children to be literate, to make the proposed method possible.

The study included a total of thirty participants from the southeast and northeast regions of Brazil, fifteen girls and fifteen boys.

The first procedure was an introductory document, which was also a step-by-step method with some important observations. The method was applied at a time when the child was receptive to writing; adults were in charge of providing the children with a lined sheet of paper and a pencil and to simply tell them the title of the story they were asked to write. The adults were required not to influence the children or give them any ideas. The children were free to write as much as they wanted and the activity was considered finished when they stopped writing.

The data was collected by a) sending an email to the children's guardians, so they could apply and then return the stories; and b) by visiting three schools—one public and two private—which authorized the application of the method on the students who wear eyeglasses.

DATA ANALYSIS

To analyze the stories, topics were defined from similar subjects present in their stories. The technique used was based on cluster analysis proposed by Mingoti (2005, pp.155-156) in which the objective is to divide the elements of the sample or population into groups so that the elements belonging to the same group are similar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stories' content analysis resulted in eight main topics according to the statements found in the written stories. These topics were grouped into four other categories created to subsidy a better understanding of the topics and the practical application (Table 1). The difference between the information provided by each gender was observed in each topic since the eyeglasses for boys and girls have formal differences.

TOPICS		DIRECT QUOTES	CATEGORY	SOME INSIGHTS ABOUT EYEGLASSES DESIGN
1	Usability	<p>“...I wear eyeglasses, I don't like to walking around with them ...”</p> <p>“... I adore my eyeglasses...”</p>	Functional	<p>Even with negative aspects, the majority declares that they like to use the product.</p> <p>Discomfort caused by disease.</p> <p>Perceived benefit of using.</p>
2	Symptoms of not using the product	<p>“... (I) remember that everyday in class I force my eyes, only to see what was written on blackboard...”</p> <p>“... I wear eyeglasses because my eyes sting and it gives me a headache...”</p>		
3	Feelings about wearing the product	<p>“...when I wear eyeglasses everything gets renewed, everything become colorful...”</p>		
4	Product Characteristics	<p>“...it was black and rounded, but I did not wear it much...”</p> <p>“...mine are batman eyeglasses...”</p> <p>“... my eyeglasses are purple light and have pink flowers...”</p> <p>“...I think my eyeglasses are pretty...”</p> <p>“...my eyeglasses are ugly...”</p>	Formal	<p>Girls talked more about product characteristics than boys.</p> <p>The most talked about characteristics by girls were: color/brand, overall look/shape and material, in this order.</p> <p>The characteristics highlighted by boys were: overall look/brand and shape, in this order.</p>
5	Product Care	<p>“... I hate it when they get dirty ... it is horrible to clean them...”</p> <p>“...they break if dropped on the floor, they get scratched, you have to take care of them and clean them...”</p>		
6	Medical exam and eye disease	<p>“...my father took me to an appointment and the doctor said – “he needs eyeglasses!”...”</p> <p>“...but to wear them you have to have an eye-test to know what your lens power is...”</p> <p>“...the first ophthalmologists looked, did a test with only one instrument and said – this girl is myopic...”</p>	Medical	<p>Boys talked more about the visit and experience of medical exams.</p> <p>The same number of boys and girls mentioned their eye disease.</p>
7	Third party opinion	<p>“...I have never been bullied because of my glasses, but I know girls who suffer a lot because of it...”</p> <p>“... sometimes wearing glasses can be bad, you can be excluded and people can call you a nerd...”</p> <p>“...my mother and father also wear them (glasses), so sometimes I wear them...”</p> <p>“... but my mother asks me to wear them (glasses)...”</p>	Reflexive	<p>The influence of family and friends appear equally.</p> <p>Few children talked about their appearance and their perception of themselves wearing glasses.</p>
8	Appearance wearing eye-glasses	<p>“... I think I look very weird wearing eyeglasses...”</p> <p>“... we look different wearing eyeglasses, I become more elegant and charming...”</p>		

Table 1. Table relating the topics grouped in categories, some insights gathered from those and also some direct quotes from the children stories.

Source: Authors (2014)

Functional Category

This category deals with functionality and correction issues in eyeglasses. The three topics were mentioned very frequently in the stories, which demonstrates the strong association of the product with its corrective function and the participants' perceptions of when the product is used or not.

The *Usability* topic was observed by both genders equally. In their stories, most children talked about whether they liked wearing glasses and the majority mentioned positive associations. Therefore, generally good product acceptance was observed, but there is still a declared aversion by some users.

In the *Symptoms of not using the product* topic, we observed that almost half of the participants talked about the many discomforts caused by refractive errors, when eyeglasses are not used. On the other hand, in the *Feelings about wearing the product* topic, most participants made a point of mentioning the benefits that the eyeglasses provide when used.

Formal Category

This category is related to the formal characteristics of the eyeglasses. In general, the two topics in this category did not appear in the texts as much as the topics relating to the functional categories, but had a good representation nonetheless. The content of the formal category is very objective and it is most directly applied by designers.

Among the *Product Characteristics* mentioned, we can see that more girls than boys talked about this topic. The most commonly talked about characteristics by girls were related to the colors of the frames. Also, positive comments were made about the product's overall look and mention of the brand was made. The shape and material of the product were less often mentioned by both genders. Among boys, the characteristics most often mentioned were the overall look (regardless of whether their comments were positive or negative), and the brand, with the same frequency and number of mentions.

The *Product Care* topic was not mentioned many times. However, the existing comments addressed specific and detailed aspects that are experienced by users. These data serve as indicative for improving issues in eyeglass designs, such as material resistance, maintenance, loss and cleaning for example.

Medical Category

The children wrote about the experience of the eye-test and their eye problems. This content is related and reinforces the functional categories of the product, since the children mentioned the reason or the time when they began to wear the product. Among the narratives, we did not find any aversion to the experience of going to the doctor and doing the tests.

The eye-test experience was more commonly mentioned by boys, and those who wrote about the visit to the ophthalmologist also wrote about their ophthalmic problems. In their stories, girls talked more about their ophthalmic problem than the eye-test.

Reflexive Category

The topics in this category report on how users see themselves and are seen when wearing the product. The stories in which the children are concerned about being perceived as good-looking, wearing eyeglasses is accompanied by negative reports about third party opinions. Therefore, in these cases, the *Appearance* topic can be interpreted as user self-assertion in defense to a bad review and stigma product. Regarding family opinion, there are cases in which the discourse of being good-looking wearing glasses is tied to parents also wearing eyeglasses. In this case, the fact that parents are wearers serves as a stimulus or positive influence for children. In general, most children mentioned the opinion and influence of others on wearing the product, as related or not with appearance, demonstrating that for some of them, there is still some concern about the stigma of wearing glasses.

The *Third Party Opinion* topic was often mentioned by both genders. Worrying about their friends' opinions, the stories were mostly related to the stigma associated to wearing the product, even when there were reports of encouragement aimed to increase the self-esteem of the user. This implied that there was a negative feeling related to wearing the product. The family was mentioned when they talked about their parents' encouragement and request that they wear the product, and when their relatives were an inspiration and a motivational force, in cases whereby they too were users.

The *Appearance* topic was not mentioned much, but with the same frequency by both genders. This demonstrates the need for self-evaluation, positive or negative, on what one looks like wearing the product. The low occurrence of the subject can also be interpreted as indicative of the product being perceived as an accessory.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

After discussing the categories, it is important to analyze the style and organization of the narratives obtained with the method. The storytelling method was applied with a broad title, enabling the children to produce any kind of story about the product, including fantastic and ludic narratives. However, in the thirty stories analyzed, from geographically distinct locations, the contents about the product discussed real issues, like emotions and experiences related to its use. This narrative structure demonstrates that eyeglasses were thought of by the children as a very pragmatic object, showing that the children think of their glasses in terms of a corrective item rather than an accessory.

The data (topics and categories) is important for the entire project because it shows the user's subjective perception of the product. The Human Center Design methodology provides data which reflects the desires and needs of users, so storytelling was an appropriate method to encourage children to write their own stories entirely without being influenced by an adult; thus, allowing for spontaneous topics to arise, without

inducing a specific subject and also bringing unusual and unexpected themes.

Also, the subjective data gathered with this method, guided the research and helped to create data for another collection method with children that is more directed and objective. Therefore, the results of those two methods with different characteristics will be analyzed and combined to define final and complete information from the children about the design guidelines for their eyeglasses.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge to FAPESP (Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo) for its financial support of this research (Process 2012/10910-1).

REFERENCES

- Bastian, W. (2000, September) As máscaras da moda. *Revista ArcDesign.*, São Paulo, 20, pp.34-40.
- Battarbee, K. (2003). Stories as shortcuts to meaning. In I. Koskinen, T. Mattelmaki, & k. Battarbee (Eds.). *Empathic Design User experience in product design.*(Chap. 3, pp. 107 -118). Finland: IT Press.
- Gozlan, E. (2007, April). Adaptação de óculos para crianças. *Revista View*, São Paulo, 79, p.52.
- Institute of Design at Stanford (2013). Retrieved August, 2013, from <http://dschool.stanford.edu/wpcontent/uploads/2011/03/BootcampBootleg2010v2SLIM.pdf>
- Krippendorff, K.(2000). Propositions of Human-centeredness: A Philosophy for Design. In D. Durling, & K. Friedman (Eds.). *Doctoral Education in Design: Foundations for the Future* (Chap.8, pp.55-63) Staffordshire (UK): Staffordshire University Press.
- Lin, M. C. L., Hughes, B. L., Katica, M. K., Dining-Zuber, C., & Plsek, P.E. (2011). Service Design and Change of Systems: Human-Centered Approaches to Implementing and Spreading Service Design. *International Journal of Design*, 5 (2),73-86.
- Mingoti, S.A. (2005). *Análise de dados através de métodos de estatística multivariada: uma abordagem aplicada*. Belo Horizonte: UFMG
- Parrish, P. (2006) Design as storytelling. *Tech Trends*, 50(4), 72-82.
- Suri, J. F. (2003). Empathic design: informed and inspired by other people's experience. In I. Koskinen, T. Mattelmaki, & k. Battarbee (Eds.). *Empathic Design User experience in product design.*(Chap.1, pp.51-58).Finland: IT Press.
- Terra, M. R. (2013). O desenvolvimento humano na teoria de Piaget. Retrieved January, 2013, from <http://www.unicamp.br/iel/site/alunos/publicacoes/textos/d00005.htm>